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INCREASING THE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN EDUCATION THROUGH THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar orqali o'quvchilarning ta'limdagi faolliklarini rivojlantirish borasida fikr yuritiladi. Shu bilan birga ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash haqida qisqacha ma'lumot beradi. Undan so'ng ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalarning muammolari va ularning kelajagi haqida munozara bo'yicha fikr yuritiladi. Axborot texnologiyalari barcha fanlar va yo'nalishlardagi umumiy bilimlarni tarqatish va ma'lumotlarni to'plash, jamlash uchun paydo bo'ldi va ta'lim jarayonidagi asosiy kuchi hisoblanadi. Ayni damda O'zbekistonning chekka hududlaridagi maktab va litsey, kollej, oliygohlarga hamraqamli texnologiyalar va mobil qurilmalar kirib borgan, buning natijasida o'quvchi yoshlar ulardan erkinlik bilan foydalanmoqdalar.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologiya, raqamli ta'lim, gadget, oliygo'h, maktab, mobil qurilma, muommolar, yechimlar, ma'lumot tarqatish.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается развитие образовательной деятельности студентов посредством цифровых технологий в образовании. При этом дается краткая информация об использовании цифровых технологий в образовании. Затем следует обсуждение проблем и будущего цифровых технологий в образовании. Информационные технологии появились как для распространения общих знаний по всем дисциплинам и направлениям, так и для сбора и обобщения информации и являются основной силой в образовательном процессе. На данный момент цифровые технологии и мобильные устройства проникли в школы и лицеи, колледжи и вузы отдаленных районов Узбекистана, в результате чего ими свободно пользуется учащаяся молодежь.

Ключевые слова: технология, цифровое образование, гаджет, вуз, школа, мобильное устройство, проблемы, решения, распространение информации.

ANNOTATION

In this article is discussed the development of students' educational activities through digital technologies in education. At the same time, it provides brief information about the use of digital technologies in education. This is followed by a discussion of the challenges and future of digital technologies in education. Information technologies appeared for the distribution of general knowledge in all disciplines and areas, and for collecting and summarizing information, and is the

main force in the educational process. At the moment, digital technologies and mobile devices have penetrated into schools and lyceums, colleges, and universities in remote areas of Uzbekistan, as a result of which young students are using them freely.

Keywords: technology, digital education, gadget, university, school, mobile device, problems, solutions, information dissemination

Introduction

In the current process of globalization, smart devices have entered all areas, and they have not left the field of education. It is no exaggeration to say that digital technologies help teachers and students learn and learn lessons as they become part of the educational process. Students gain knowledge and understanding of the digital systems, data and processes involved in creating digital solutions, realizing that they can play an active role in meeting current and future needs.[11].

If you look at the history and current stages of such devices, you can see that they are divided into 3 branches: digital systems, data and information, and the creation of digital solutions[12].

1 **Digital systems.** It includes hardware, software and network components. Students and teachers will first learn about different hardware and software and understand how data is transferred between components in a system and how hardware and software interact to form networks, they will learn the secret and put it into practice.

2. **Data and information.** In this situation, students focus on how data is collected and presented, and how it is interpreted in context to obtain information. Students will learn how data is represented and structured for use by digital systems, as well as methods for collecting, managing and organizing data used to solve problems, generate and communicate ideas and information.

3. **Creation of digital solutions.** As a pupils, students learn the interconnected processes and skills that create digital solutions with the help of a teacher. Students will participate in four processes of analysis, design, development and evaluation. Creating digital solutions requires skills in the use of digital systems and computing, design and systems thinking, and secure interaction using appropriate technical and social protocols[12].

The free use of digital technologies in education creates social activity among students and encourages them to be active in all areas of life. Information technologies appeared to disseminate general knowledge in all disciplines and areas, to collect and generalize information and are the main force in the educational process. At the moment, mobile devices have penetrated schools and lyceums, colleges and universities in remote areas of Uzbekistan, and young students freely use them. Among them, we can include new technologies such as: mobile devices, smart boards, tablets, laptops, virtual laboratories. It is correct to say that the introduction of teaching aids with their help is changing education in schools and institutions, making a significant contribution to improving the quality of education[9,10]. The effective use of technology in education is constantly trying to create new solutions to increase access to education for individuals who do not have access to appropriate educational tools. As we watch digital technology enter education, we see that it has come a long way as a learning tool. At the same time, we see that almost all teachers and students use social networks as an important element of the overall e-learning experience. Social networks are by far the most convenient place for exchanging information on current topics. You can freely exchange information from Internet networks anywhere and anytime. In addition, applicants, schoolchildren, students, graduates can use social networks and digital technologies at a convenient time when enrolling, transferring to study, and this situation is not only convenient for them, but also a great opportunity to save time.

When lessons are taught in the traditional way, the classroom environment does not support the learning process, faster assessment and more active participation. In this case, we are confident that digital learning technologies will fill this gap. As smartphones and other wireless technology devices become more and more popular among the general public, schools and educational institutions should take advantage of technology by introducing it into the classroom. In fact, the flexibility and compactness of current technologies make learning more attractive to the next generation. Some researchers, i.e. traditional teachers, view digital technology in the classroom as a

distraction for students[6,8]. People all over the world are aware of the disaster caused by the coronavirus epidemic. In a crisis, digital technologies at least maintain the stability of the education system. Students study without leaving home[3,4].

Main body.

It is no exaggeration to say that the effective use of digital technologies allows students to communicate with friends anywhere in the world, exchange information and travel to those places through their gadgets. Schoolchildren and students can participate in online classes and listen to speakers from foreign universities without leaving their homes. During the world-famous pandemic, teachers and teachers in the education system of Uzbekistan, especially in higher education, organized their classes through the Zoom platform. They opened a special official group in Telegram channels, gave assignments during classes and monitored their implementation. We can say that this, in turn, made both the teacher and the student comfortable. Online classes have both good and bad sides. First, in terms of side effects, children who were active in offline classes became lazy in online classes, or vice versa. Since actively studying students had a lot of free time during online classes, their interest in gadgets and mobile phones increased, and as a result, cases of their addiction to mobile games were also observed.

If we look at the Haims program that operates in the higher education system of Uzbekistan, it allows students to register regularly to receive information about course materials and assignments, complete assignments and put them back on the Internet. In this situation, the teacher regularly accessed the Internet, that is, the heims program, to respond to students, check and grade their assignments.

Schools play an important role in the beginning of our lives for all of us, and their closure during the pandemic has negative consequences for the psychological well-being of many families and children. Digital technologies have come to the rescue in this situation. This motivated us to easily overcome difficulties and work more deeply on our knowledge. Another advantage of the online learning system is that it allows students to pause and repeat tasks given by the teacher, watch videos and study the course content on their own. Taking quizzes is another active learning strategy that educational technology can support. Students can start working on a project together in class and quickly collaborate, communicate, and share ideas with each other using social media, interactive whiteboards, and other technologies. Physical and social constraints allow students to collaborate from anywhere, at any time. Technology also allowed learners to engage in spontaneous discussions and get immediate answers to any questions or questions about a topic, and most importantly, comparisons were possible. From the environmental impact of using less paper for handouts and books, to saving time and simplifying research, digital learning can reduce costs, make better use of resources, promote sustainability, and expand student and educator outreach[5,6]. Technology is a widespread and interconnected phenomenon in many aspects of modern life and society. The digital revolution that has swept the world has begun to permeate the field of education. It is rapidly changing the way students learn, and as a result, technology is expected to improve education by making it more affordable and accessible[7].

In the process of writing this article, we have seen that while technology will play an important role in shaping the future of education, a new generation of teachers who understand the importance of human interaction in the classroom is required to ensure the effective use of new teaching methods. tools. This can lead to interesting discussions and debates in the field of education. The next generation, who are the successors of today and tomorrow, should be able to effectively use additional devices, not forgetting the role and role of teachers and coaches in the perfect knowledge of digital technologies in education, which are important for them. Parental control is also important in this regard. In the future, students and youth education trends will follow the increasing possibilities of the Internet and network bandwidth, which will help to introduce innovative technologies into the classroom. Thus, we have arrived at the era of hybrid teaching and learning, where online and offline systems are combined to improve results.

Conclusion

The use of digital technologies in classrooms and classrooms not only creates comfort for pupils and students, but also creates the basis for self-study of foreign languages. Learning English individually, at home at a convenient time using digital technologies will stimulate their further development. The most effective way to reduce the amount of repetitive, time-consuming teacher tasks in traditional classrooms is to use technology in the classroom. Educational technology applications can save a lot of time and energy by automating day-to-day operations such as attendance tracking and performance monitoring. In addition, it allows parents to always control the grades received in each lesson, and at the same time check whether their child has entered or left school. Teachers teach students how to use technology responsibly and strategically, which helps them make decisions, work on themselves, and develop self-discipline. Technology in education helps prepare students for lifelong learning. These technologies provide students with the freedom to access the virtual world and digital knowledge according to their own learning style. Students can learn at their own pace with digital content creation tools that tailor teaching and learning. The digital classroom uses electronic devices and software to teach students and integrates technology into the learning process. The traditional classroom is being transformed into a digital classroom with the help of computers and the Internet. Students can learn more effectively and track their progress with technology and sophisticated tools. We have no doubt that in the future, students will create even simpler and more convenient technologies, because today's generation is a child of the technical age.

The list of used literature

1. A.J. Cañas, J.W. Coffey, M.J. Carnot, P. Feltovich, R.R. Hoffman, J. Feltovich, J.D. Novak, A summary of literature pertaining to the use of concept mapping techniques and technologies for education and performance support, Report to the Chief of Naval Education and Training (2003) 1–108.
2. B. Cavas, P. Cavas, B. Karaoglan, T. Kisla, A Study on Science Teachers' Attitudes Toward Information and Communications Technologies in Education, Online Sub- mission 8 (2) (2009).
3. G. Emmanuel, A. Sife, Challenges of managing information and communication technologies for education: EXperiences from Sokoine National Agricultural Li- brary, International journal of education and development using ICT 4 (3) (2008).
4. G. Kostopoulos, S. Kotsiantis, EXploiting semi-supervised learning in the education field: A critical survey, in: Advances in Machine Learning/Deep Learning-Based Technologies, 2022, pp. 79–94.
5. M.A. Camilleri, A.C. Camilleri, Digital learning resources and ubiquitous technologies in education, Technology, Knowledge and Learning 22 (1) (2017) 65–82.
6. M. Beardsley, L. Albó, P. Aragón, D. Hernández-Leo, Emergency education effects on teacher abilities and motivation to use digital technologies, British Journal of Educational Technology (2021).
7. K. Yordanova, Mobile learning and integration of advanced technologies in education, in: Proceedings of the 2007 international conference on Computer systems and technologies, 2007, June, pp. 1–6.
8. T.A. Vakaliuk, O.M. Spirin, N.M. Lobanchykova, L.A. Martseva, I.V. Novitska, V.V. Kontsedailo, Features of distance learning of cloud technologies for the quar- antine organisation's educational process, J. Phys. Conf. Ser. 1840 (1) (2021, March) 012051.
9. J. Keengwe, M. Bhargava, Mobile learning and integration of mobile technologies in education, Education and Information Technologies 19 (4) (2014) 737–746.
10. P.L. Rogers, Barriers to adopting emerging technologies in education, Journal of educational computing research 22 (4) (2000) 455–472.
11. <https://www.education.vic.gov.au/school/teachers/teachingresources/discipline/technologies/Pages/digitaltechnologies.aspx>
12. <https://victoriancurriculum.vcaa.vic.edu.au/technologies/digital-technologies/introduction/structure>

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